

Micro Finance as a Boon for Rural Poor

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 7

Special Issue : 3

Month : February

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Bhuvanewari, H., and M. Sivabalaji. "Micro Finance as a Boon for Rural Poor." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 7, no. S3, 2019, pp. 27–30.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2572411>

Introduction

India is a land of villages. Nearly 74% of the total population is living in rural areas. A significant large number of them are poor. The microcredit program in India is now the largest in the world. Since independence, the Government of India and the Reserve Bank of India and the Reserve Bank of India have made concerted efforts to provide the poor with access to credit. Despite the phenomenal increase in the past several decades, the rural poor continue to depend on informal source of credit. Besides all the things, cumbersome procedure and risk perceptions of the banks left a gap in serving the credit needs of rural poor. In this context, microcredit has emerged as the most suitable and practical alternative to the conventional banking in reaching the hitherto poor population.

Micro-finance has been recognized as a tool for extending banking services to the poor and the needy and for poverty alleviation. The Reserve Bank has been making efforts since 1992 to create an environment for orderly development of micro-finance recognizing its potential to positively influence the upliftment of the rural poor.

Major Players of Microfinance

- Government of India
- NABARD
- Banks
- NGO/MFI

Today's Trend

Microfinance is a profitable opportunity to deploy their funds or atleast a cost efficient way of meeting their priority sector targets. The larger of the 2 main models, SHG-Banks linkage programmed covered about 143 million poor households in March 2016 and provided indirect access to the banking system to another 14 million. The RBI has observed MF system faced certain challenges such as regional imbalance, quality of the SHGs, high cost of delivery emergency of SHG federation, etc. It also noted that MFI model was comparatively costlier in delivery of financial services because of low volume and size of the loan.

Principles for Best Microfinance Practices

- Enabling financial services, just not loans but also savings, insurance and money transfer services.
- Microfinance should help poor households to raise income and to build assets.
- Do not always depend on donors and Government for financial need. Microfinance must pay for itself.
- Micro finance should be built in permanent local institutions.
- Integrating the financial needs of poor people into the country's mainstream financial system.
- Donor should focus on capacity building.
- Transparency in interest rates.
- MFIS should measure and disclose their performance both financial and socially.

Need of Microfinance in India

- In India, institutional credit agencies made an entry in rural areas initially to provide an alternative to rural money lenders who provided credit support, but not without exploiting the rural poor.
- There are 2 main factors that count to the bringing up of microfinance as a policy in India.
- The second national policy that has had a significant impact on the evolution of the India's banking and financial system is the integrated rural development programme introduced in 1978 and designed to be a direct instrument for attacking India's rural poverty. This programme is interesting to the study because it was a larger program whose main thrust was to alleviate poverty through the provision of loans and it was considered a failure.
- The last major event which had impact on the financial and banking system in India was the liberalization of India's financial system in 1990s characterized by reforms of structural adjustments and financial policy reforms initiated by the Reserve Bank of India.
- The search for an alternative mechanism for catering to the financial services needs of the poor was thus becoming imperative.
- Microfinance has proved as a boon for the rural poor.
- More than 8.5 lakh SHGs are functioning successfully in India.
- Innumerable poor families got sustainable financial services through it.
- Besides the big donor agencies like NABARD, SIDB, etc. there are 2800 partner NGOs working extensively in the field.
- Huge participation of corporate icons in Microfinance are also witnessed like HLL's project Sakthi and ITC's woman empowerment project.
- Many foreign agencies are working comprehensively in this field like CARE-CASHE.
- About 20 per cent of the Micro financial Intermediaries are registered as societies.
- About 20 per cent are trust.
- About 65 percent of MFIs follow the operating model of SHGs.
- Large concentration in South India.
- 600 MFI initiatives have a cumulative outreach of 1.25 crore poor households.
- NABARD's bank linkage programme has cumulatively reached a total of 9.4 lakhs with about 1.4 crore households.

Challenges of Sound Commercial Micro financial Practices

The microfinance industry's objective is to satisfy the unmet demand on a much larger scale and to play a role in reducing poverty for sustainable economic development. While much progress has been made in developing a viable, commercial microfinance sector in the last few decades, several issues

need to be addressed. The obstacles or challenges in building a sound commercial microfinance industry include.

- In appropriate donor subsidies.
- Poor regulation and supervision of deposit-taking MFIS.
- Few MFIS that meet the needs for savings, remittances or insurance.
- Limited management capacity in MFIS.
- Institutional inefficiencies.
- Need for more dissemination and adoption of rural, agriculture microfinance methodologies.
- Non affordability cost of funds from ultimate borrower.
- Operations of MFIS are not transparent.
- Absence of regulatory mechanism.
- Lack of accountability.
- Indulgence in unethical practices reported in certain quarters.

Future Strategies for Microfinance Innovations

NABARD as a strategic policy, has pioneered in formulation of development programmes together with appropriate guidelines in the areas of microfinance. This has been possible through continuous innovations based on programme approach, linking support organizations with the credit institutions through their essential support mechanism such as training, organizing and capacity building etc. of client institutions, and non-governmental organizations for strengthening microfinance activities in the country.

The prominent among the various initiatives and innovations that have taken place in fostering the growth of microfinance sector with the active innovations that have take place in fostering the growth of microfinance sector with the active involvement of NABARD include bank credit and finance services fund assistance to NGO, development initiative for North-Eastern region and KBK region of Orissa, capacity building of partner institutions, creation of microfinance development fund, establishing collaboration with external donor agencies. In the area of SHG-bank linkages programmed etc. The national policy on microfinance should emphasize on encouraging initiative and participation of different types of institution involved, with in the regulation and supervision by component authorities, creating policy environment for closer linkages of the microfinance sector with the formal banking channels and making available equity, start-up capital and capacity-building funds for the existing and prospective institutions engaged in micro-finance.

The strategies for micro finance must also be matched by a strategy for raising agricultural productivity through creation of appropriate infrastructure in the critical areas such as irrigation, soil and water conservation, plant protection, agro-processing, post-harvest management, rural roads, agriculture marketing etc. Such an integrated strategy will also place a heavy demand on credit for productivity in farm sector, it is necessary to promote accelerated growth of rural non-form sector, on which a large number of rural poor are heavily dependent for their livelihood support through creation of gainful employment opportunities.

Conclusion

Some valuable lessons can be drawn from the experience of successful Microfinance operation. First of all, the poor repay their loans and are willing to pay for higher interest rates than commercial banks provided that access to credit is provided. In order to be sustainable, microfinance lending should be grounded on market principles because large scale lending cannot be accomplished through subsidies. Eventually it would be ideal to enhance the creditworthiness of the poor and to make them more “bankable” to financial institutions have a lot to contributes to this by building financial discipline and educating borrowers about repayment requirements.

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